

model2bio
waste-to-feedstock

Website and social media channels

Deliverable 8.2

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Technical References

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Modifications	Author
0.1	21 August 2020	First draft version based on beta website version	María Teresa López Bertani, ESCI
0.2	1 September 2020	Second draft version	Tamara Fernández Arévalo, CEIT
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Summary

The website www.model2bio.eu contains public information about the project: the abstract, part or phases of the project, the partners working on it, the solutions to the economic and environmental problems, all with the branding and design described in the communication and dissemination plan. Topics covered by the website are summarised in the present deliverable, describing the content of each. Moreover, are provided descriptions about website structure, features and other important aspects such as update procedures.

The present deliverable is 'DEC', in nature. For convenience, we provide a short report below about the website and the social media channels on LinkedIn and Twitter.

The Model2Bio website is set up along the details of Subtasks 8.1.1 described in work plan table of Annex 1 "Bio-based Industries Research and Innovation Action" of the Grant Agreement and the rules governing in the Consortium Agreement signed by the partners.

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1 Model2Bio website design, structure and implementation

As part of initial activities of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, ESCI has implemented this project website. A choice between several options for the domain name of the Model2Bio website resulted in the following domain: www.model2bio.eu.

The overall objective of the Model2Bio project website, is to be the reference point and digital meeting place for the scientific and professional communities, the end users and the general public. It contains all the institutional information about the Model2Bio project.

During the first phase of the project, the website will present a project overview, the main objectives and the description of the technologies that the project will be working in. It will establish links to social media channels and publish relevant updates.

At a later stage, with the results available, the website will contain latest updates and will act as the platform to distribute non-confidential contents (scientific publications, articles, press releases, interviews, project updates, etc.)

The repository for the partners, containing working documents and deliverables through a reserved partners' area, is not part of this deliverable and it is managed by CEIT, the coordinator institution.

The navigation within the website is easy and straightforward with pages accessible from the home page and subpages. At the current stage of the project, the website will be launched with a light, but essential, structure that could be enhanced and enlarged as more contents are generated by the project.

The main structure and the main features of the Model2Bio website and an outlook for further features are presented.

2 Structure

The website is structured in a homepage and six sub sections:

Figure 1 Model2Bio website structure

2.1 Homepage

The main elements of the homepage have been developed in order to give the site visitors a concise and short overview of Model2Bio project. The homepage has a vertical navigation bar utilising the most common user eye-scanning pattern to grab the attention of visitors.

At the top it provides a small animation of a mathematical equation and a sentence that explain the project: “A pioneering decision support tool, based on mathematical models, to predict agro-food residual streams and to identify best routes for valorising them”.

The navigation bar to go to other pages is a horizontal located at the top right. Horizontal navigation bars are easier for people to navigate once they stay on the website and want to discover the content in more detail.

At the top and the bottom of the homepage links to the social media channels are given.

The bottom of the Homepage provides additional important information, such as legal information.

Figure 2: Homepage layout (bottom part)

Figure 3 Homepage layout (second part)

Figure 4 Homepage layout (third part)

Figure 5 Homepage layout (bottom part)

2.2 The project

“The project” section is the densest and include the majority of the project’s information. In order to present the content in a user- friendly way, five subsections have been created.

2.2.1 About

In the About subsection is presented the context of the project, the concept and who is the group working on the project.

2.2.2 Expected results

In the Expected Results subsection are presented the concrete outcomes that are going to be ready for the end of the project, in M 36.

2.2.3 Impacts

In the Impact subsection are included the importance of the outcomes, in terms of knowledge, the industry, the economy and the environment.

2.2.4 Solutions

In the Solutions subsection is described the importance of the solutions to actual agrifood residual stream problems that the software (Decision Support System Tool) is going to provide.

2.2.5 Technical Elements

In the Technical Elements subsection, are explained the components that are part of the Decision Support System Tool.

Figure 6 The project tab

2.3 Partners

The page “Partners” is composed by two subsections.

2.3.1 About the Company

Each organisation of the Model2Bio consortium is presented with its logo with a link to its website.

2.3.2 The role in the project

A description of the specific activities and responsibilities in the Model2Bio project.

Figure 7 Partners tab

2.4 Industries

The page “Industries” is composed by 4 Icons and texts representing the 4 production lines that are going to be considered to create the Simulation Module and therefore the final tool: Vegetable, Meat, Dairy and Alcoholic Beverages.

Figure 8 Model2Bio Industries tab

2.5 News & Events

The page “News & Events” currently includes just one press release; but as the project progresses it will include other press releases, news, journalistic articles, interviews and events related to the project. It will be updated often with new information in order to keep the audience aware of this project progress. ESCI in cooperation with the coordinator and / or project partners will feed the News sections.

Concerning the news, meetings execution, important milestones achieved as for proper project execution and any other relevant information about project ongoing will be included here. Furthermore, press releases as well as articles will be published. Finally, events related to the project such as meetings, workshops or conferences will be scheduled and described in order to contribute to proper project dissemination.

In addition, the current Twitter lead will be displayed so that viewers can quickly review the latest Twitter feeds and subscribe to it, if they want.

Figure 9 Model2Bio News and Events tab

2.6 Resources

In this section scientific publications, the institutional Power Point presentation, the audio-visual pieces (1 explanatory promotional video and 2 video news releases) and the best practice flipbook will be included.

Figure 10 Model2Bio Resources tab

2.7 Contact

This section provides information about the email addresses where website users can address in order to establish contact with the project consortium.

Figure 11 Model2Bio Contact tab

3 Content updates and maintenance

ESCI involved staff will be responsible for managing the website and driving website updates on a regular basis. News will be updated monthly and press releases, publications and events will be posted in a timely manner as well. Additionally, technical infrastructure of the site is developed by ANAXIMANDRE, who is also responsible for maintenance and hosting.

The website is built on the WordPress platform. The layout is responsive to various devices, allowing easy use from smartphones and tablets, as illustrated below:

Figure 12 Website layout on smart phone

4 The Model2Bio LinkedIn Site

LinkedIn targets career-minded professionals, who are interested in the project, and prefer to follow this social media, rather than using Twitter or visiting the website on a regular basis. Parallel to the launch of the website www.model2bio.eu, also the LinkedIn Page of Model2Bio has been set up.

The address to the LinkedIn page is: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/model2bio/about>
The first post was published on 15th May 2020, announcing the start of the project and the Kick- Off Meeting.

Figure 13 Model2Bio LinkedIn page

5 The Model2Bio TWITTER Feed

Twitter allows members to network via 160-character messages or tweets. The Twitter channel for the Model2Bio project was established in May 2020. The chosen address is @Model2bioEu. The first tweet was announcing the project start, and the Kick- Off Meeting. The partners have already started re-tweeting Model2Bio news, which has resulted in a steady increase in activity.

Figure 14 Model2Bio Twitter Account